

FUNDAMENTALS OF GROWING ECOLOGICALLY CLEAN COTTON FIBER

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Abstract: It should be noted that in recent years, due to the sharp drop in air temperature in some regions of our Republic, there has been an increase in various sucking insects and pests such as whitefly, candala, sticky bacteriosis, penicillosis, aspergillois, black aphid (cotton aphid).

Keywords: pyrethroid, allergic effect, cotton, poison, cyclopropane, endoparasite, pure substance.

Further development and improvement of the cotton sector in our republic, development of resource- and resource-saving advanced agrotechnologies for growing high-quality products at low cost are considered urgent tasks of agriculture.

Defoliation of cotton is also important for quick and high-quality harvesting of the cotton crop grown in the republic without leaving it to cold and rainy days.

Cotton defoliation increases the crop image during cotton harvest. If this agrotechnical factor is carried out on time and with good quality, it ensures complete shedding of cotton leaves. Especially, it does not allow the newly emerging small leaves to grow, as a result, air aeration between the rows of cotton is improved and it effectively uses sunlight and heat.

Also, the effect of the defoliant on the cotton body, especially the leaves, is effective. Due to the process of physiological formation in the leaves, the available nutrients in the plant body and leaves are redistributed to the elements of the crop (I. Imomaliev 1977, K. Abdusattorov 2007). As a result, the rate of ripening of the pods and their opening accelerates.

It should be noted that in recent years, due to the sharp drop in air temperature in some regions of our Republic, there has been an increase in various sucking insects and pests such as whitefly, candala, sticky bacteriosis, penicillosis, aspergillois, black aphid (cotton aphid). Studying the level of their spread and the dynamics of development in the cotton field is inextricably linked to the effectiveness of chemical and biological control measures (B.Mamatov, S.Uljaev 2007).

Depending on the condition of the plants in the cotton bolls, some pests and insects cause contamination of the cotton fiber in the open bolls with sticky sap. Various fungi develop on the fiber covered with sticky sap. In most cases, the cotton fibers stick together and become contaminated, and conditions for the development of saprophytic fungi are created here. As a result, the surface and upper part of the cotton fiber standing in the pans becomes blackened and damaged. In the language of the peasants, it is said that cotton is covered with black aphid.

One of the worst complications of black aphid is that it continues to damage cotton stored in bundles at cotton processing stations, causing a large amount of cotton to deteriorate.

The main wintering and spreading places for these are cold-resistant shora, dog grape, saffron, ajrik, especially weeds such as ivy and sheep thorn. In the field conditions, it spreads and causes more damage due to the violation of external agrotechnical factors, especially in the areas where the seedlings are prematurely uniformed, planted more than the norm, not pruned on time, overgrown, overgrown, and dormant. Because the air circulation makes it difficult for the plant to breathe, and with the increase of moisture, the buds that appeared early in the lower layers of the cotton become black. The exposed lint sticks to the hand like sticky glue on the white cotton, and the black sap causes the cotton fiber to mold.

As a result, the quality of the cotton raw material is significantly reduced, the color is damaged, the fiber becomes unsuitable for the production of quality products, and the productivity of the equipment and work equipment of the processing industry is drastically reduced.

In conclusion, in order to grow environmentally friendly cotton fiber, it is advisable to implement the following measures during the growing season of cotton in order to reduce and eliminate the level of damage by insects that have a negative effect on the quality of the fiber.

1. In order to harvest the cotton crop without leaving it to the rain or cold, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following with timely cotton defoliation;
2. Removal of common weeds in cotton fields, such as shura, dog grape, gulkhairi, ajrik, koypechak, koytikan;
3. Based on the characteristics of the cotton variety planted on the cotton fields, leave the normal number of seedlings, remove the excess from the field by harvesting;

4. Organization of timely irrigation;
 5. High-quality processing between rows without damaging the root system of cotton;
 6. Carrying out cotton retailing within the specified periods and on time;
- Fulfillment of such factors within the specified time and in the norm creates opportunities for growing environmentally friendly cotton fibre.

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